

Kinetic and Mechanistic Study of Substitution Reaction of the Aqua-ligands from Hexa-aquochromium(III) Ion by Glutamic Acid

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Manuscript received 2 February 1990, revised 1 March 1991, accepted 31 May 1991

Kinetics of substitution of aqua-ligands from hexa-aquochromium(III) ion by glutamic acid (GluH) in aqueous medium has been studied spectrophotometrically and the rate law has been established at pH 2.7. The reaction rate is found to be pH-dependent in the pH range 2.0–5.0. Activation parameter have been calculated and compared with water-exchange reaction and other substitution reactions of hexa-aquochromium(III) ion. A mechanism involving outer sphere association between the two reactant species followed by transformation of this outer sphere complex into the product by associative path has been suggested.

LIGAND substitution reactions in octahedral complexes have been studied by many workers and the results indicate that in Cr^{III} systems the reaction proceed in both I_a and I_b paths. Anation of $[\text{Cr}(\text{H}_2\text{O})_6]^{3+}$ by a series of organic anions like oxalate, malonate, citrate, acetate etc., proceed by S_N1 (dissociative) pathway as observed by Hamm *et al.*¹. Banerjee *et al.* observed that anation reactions of $[\text{Cr}(\text{H}_2\text{O})_6]^{3+}$ with oxalate² and malonate³ proceed through outer sphere association followed by dissociative path for the transformation of the outer sphere to the inner sphere product. On the contrary the experimental results led the authors³ to propose an associative character for the aquo-ligand substitution in $[\text{Cr}(\text{H}_2\text{O})_6]^{3+}$ by glycine⁴. The anation reactions of $[\text{Cr}(\text{H}_2\text{O})_6]^{3+}$ by NCS⁻ was studied by Postumus and King⁵ and the rate law derived by them shows first order dependence in $[\text{NCS}^-]$. The present communication deals with the results obtained in the anation of $[\text{Cr}(\text{H}_2\text{O})_6]^{3+}$ by glutamic acid, a bidentate (N, O donor) ligand.

Experimental

Hexa-aquochromium(III) perchlorate (A.R.) was prepared by the reported method⁶. The absorption spectrum of complex I ($[\text{Cr}(\text{H}_2\text{O})_6](\text{ClO}_4)_3$) exhibited λ_{max} at 410 nm ($\log \epsilon$ 1.15) and 750 nm ($\log \epsilon$ = 1.23). The product of the reaction between $[\text{Cr}(\text{H}_2\text{O})_6]^{3+}$ and glutamic acid was prepared by mixing the two reactants in different molar ratios, viz. 1 : 1, 1 : 2, 1 : 3, 1 : 5, 1 : 10 thermostated at 45° for 72 h. Absorption spectra of all the mixtures were exhibited similar λ_{max} at 410 and 560 nm. The composition of the product in solution was determined by Job's method of continuous variation. The metal ligand ratio was found to be 1 : 2.

Kinetic experiments were carried out spectrophotometrically using a Shimadzu spectrophotometer. pH of the reaction was adjusted by NaOH/HClO₄ using

a Systronics digital pH meter. Ionic strength of the reaction medium was adjusted by adding NaClO₄. The course of the reaction was followed by measuring absorbances at 560 nm where a difference existed in the spectra of the complex I and complex II (product).

The concentration of the ligand was always maintained high so that the pseudo-first order rate law could be applied. The pseudo-first order rate constants (k_{obs}) were determined graphically.

Results and Discussion

Effect of varying [complex I] on reaction rate : At a fixed excess concentration (0.075 M) of glutamic acid, ionic strength (μ) 0.032 M and pH 2.7, the [complex I] was varied. The values of k_{obs} were found to be 9.39×10^{-5} , 9.41×10^{-5} and 9.40×10^{-5} at [complex I] of 0.0025, 0.0035 and 0.004 M respectively at 50°. The experimental data indicate that the rate of the reaction is first order with respect to [complex I],

$$\frac{d[\text{complex II}]}{dt} = k_{\text{obs}} [\text{complex I}]$$

Effect of varying pH on rate constant : The rate of the reaction increased with the increase of pH of the medium. At a fixed [complex I] (0.0025 M), [Glutamic acid] (0.075 M), μ (0.032 M) and temperature (50°), the pseudo-first order rate constants were determined (Table 1).

TABLE 1—VARIATION OF RATE CONSTANTS (k_{obs}) WITH GLUTAMIC ACID AT DIFFERENT pH

pH	$k_{\text{obs}} (\times 10^5 \text{ s}^{-1})$
2.0	8.75
2.7	10.85
3.5	15.00
4.0	18.29
4.5	20.79

variation of incoming ligand concentration on reaction rate,

The rate equation for the anation can be deduced in the form,

$$\frac{d[\text{Cr}(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2(\text{Glu})_2]^+}{dt} = \frac{k_a K_E [\text{Cr}(\text{H}_2\text{O})_6^{3+}]_{\text{Total}} [\text{Glu.H}]}{1 + K_E [\text{Glu.H}]} = k_{\text{obs}} [\text{Cr}(\text{H}_2\text{O})_6^{3+}]_{\text{Total}} \quad (2)$$

$$\text{or,} \quad k_{\text{obs}} = \frac{k_a K_E [\text{Glu.H}]}{1 + K_E [\text{Glu.H}]} \quad (3)$$

$$\text{or,} \quad 1/k_{\text{obs}} = 1/k_a + 1/k_a K_E [\text{Glu.H}] \quad (4)$$

where, K_E is ion-pair equilibrium constant and k_a the rate constant for interchange of outer sphere complex to inner sphere complex. So plot of $1/k_{\text{obs}}$ vs $1/[\text{Glu.H}]$ should be a straight line with an intercept of $1/k_a$ and a slope of $1/k_a K_E$. This is found to be true for all the temperature studied. The k_a values determined from the intercepts are given in Table 3. The K_E values are almost constant.

Results of anation of some analogous systems are cited in Table 4 for comparison and it appears that there is a definite dependence of rate of reaction on the nature of incoming ligand. The anation rate of the title complex is high in comparison with the isotopic water exchange process, which suggests an associative interchange mechanism in the substitution reaction.

TABLE 3—VALUES OF k_a AND K_E FOR ANATION BY GLUTAMIC ACID AT DIFFERENT TEMPERATURES

Temp. °C	$k_a \times 10^5 \text{ s}^{-1}$	K_E
40	8.09	9.5
45	10.25	9.8
50	24.45	9.8
55	31.21	9.9

TABLE 4—COMPARISON OF k_a AND ACTIVATION PARAMETERS OF ANALOGOUS SYSTEMS

System	$k_a \text{ s}^{-1}$	$\Delta H^\ddagger \text{ kJ mol}^{-1}$	$\Delta S^\ddagger \text{ JK mol}^{-1}$
$\text{Cr}(\text{H}_2\text{O})_6^{3+} - \text{OH}_2(\text{ex})^a$	0.41×10^{-5}	109.2	11.7
$\text{Cr}(\text{H}_2\text{O})_6^{3+} + \text{glycine}^b$	1.2×10^{-3}	52.08	42.84
$\text{Cr}(\text{H}_2\text{O})_6^{3+} + \text{oxalate}^b$	8.97×10^{-3}	121.80	59.22
$\text{Cr}(\text{H}_2\text{O})_6^{3+} + \text{malonate}^c$	3.70×10^{-3}	102.48	-0.55
$\text{Cr}(\text{H}_2\text{O})_6^{3+} + \text{glutamic acid}^d$	4.46×10^{-5}	73.5	-86.10

^aRef. 7. ^bRef. 4. ^cRef. 3. ^dPresent work. ^eAt 35°.
^fAt 40°.

Effect of varying ionic strength on rate constant : The [complex I], [ligand], pH and temperature were kept fixed at 0.0025 M, 0.075 M, 2.7 and 50° respectively. The values of k_{obs} were found to be 10.95×10^{-5} , 10.99×10^{-5} and $11.01 \times 10^{-5} \text{ s}^{-1}$ for ionic strengths 0.282, 0.532 and 0.782 M respectively. Thus variation of μ by NaClO_4 did not alter the rate of reaction which is expected for a reaction involving a cationic and a zwitterionic species.

Effect of temperature on reaction rate : The reaction rate was followed at four different temperatures for different [ligand] to find out the effect of temperature on the value of rate constants for interchange process. Activation parameters were calculated from the linear Eyring plot of $\log k_a/T$ vs $1/T$ and values of $\Delta H^\ddagger$ and $\Delta S^\ddagger$ are 73.5 kJ mol⁻¹ and -86.10 JK mol⁻¹ respectively.

Mechanism and conclusion : It appears from Table 4 that in case of glutamic acid substitution, the interchange rate constant is much faster than the isotopic water exchange rate constant at a common temperature. The activation enthalpy for glutamic acid substitution in $\text{Cr}(\text{H}_2\text{O})_6^{3+}$ is lower than the corresponding parameter for water exchange process. This result suggests an associative character of the interchange process. Further it can be seen that the entropies of activation for glutamic acid substitution is negative which is expected for an associative process. The mechanism of the anation reaction is shown in Scheme 2.

Scheme 2

References

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